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Policy to facilitate effective business support: What can we learn from England's Business Link?

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Executive summary

Governments seeking to support entrepreneurs and small businesses can draw valuable lessons from the history of enterprise policy. England's Business Link (1992-2012) provides an interesting case from which to learn lessons of contemporary relevance. It sought to operate as a single point of contact for businesses seeking support. Reviewing the evidence on the running and impacts of Business Link, we highlight lessons for policymakers. Specifically, brokerage models can enhance effectiveness, catering to diverse business needs throughout their development journey. Furthermore, recognising the dynamic nature of business support presents opportunities for timely engagement, ensuring providers intervene at critical stages. Finally, a well-defined national business support brand that balances consistency with local flexibility and innovation can serve as a foundation for sustained impact.

Learning the lessons of the past

Governments internationally seek to maximise the benefits of enterprise policies supporting entrepreneurs and small businesses (OECD, 2020). As today's business support landscape undergoes change, there is value in learning lessons from the history of enterprise policy.

Our research on the historical development of UK enterprise policy has examined archival records, policy documents, evaluations and contemporary studies (Mallett and Wapshott, 2020). Business Link (1992-2012) remains the most high-profile business support intervention seen in

England and provides a valuable resource for learning about what works, for whom and when. Business Link has been extensively evaluated and researched, with variations over time and across regions (and with similar schemes continuing in the other nations of the UK and internationally). In this policy brief, we explore evaluations of the Business Link programme to identify insights for current debates.

Business Link: National support for SMEs

Business Link was set up in 1992 to help relieve small business owners from the burdens of bureaucracy. It was intended to operate as a single point of contact for businesses seeking support. Business Link represented a decentralised model, organised through local franchises. It grew to provide support through 89 regional offices and up to 650 Personal Business Advisors (Centre for Cities, 2013).

While operationally decentralised, the Business Link brand was carefully controlled. The government was keen to ensure appropriate service levels were delivered, with Business Link operators required to hold appropriate standards and accreditations. The decentralised model, and features of its implementation, led to spatial fragmentation of the availability of guidance and support for SMEs, with business owners being funnelled into local Business Link services with a local monopoly rather than accessing a national market for such services in the ways that a large firm might do (Bryson and Daniels, 1998). Bennett and Robson (2004) reported that service varied between, and even within, different types of franchise (e.g. those provided through local government, Chambers of Commerce or the private sector), highlighting variations in market penetration, impact and satisfaction.

Evaluations were undertaken at different times, in different regions and by different means. Positive impacts were identified, though these varied. Satisfaction improved through the running of the programme, with impacts more common in terms of 'soft' outcomes (e.g. management skills) rather than 'hard' outcomes (e.g. productivity, profits or turnover, Bennett, 2007). Nonetheless, the scale, cost and bottom-line impacts of the programme faced criticisms, and it was phased out, finally closing in 2012 (Mallett and Wapshott, 2020).

Key insights

Branding and building trust

Small businesses can struggle to navigate business support provision, which they experience as fragmented and hard to evaluate. Business Link offered a unified brand, providing a 'one stop shop' for businesses in search of support. Having a single point of contact under an established brand enables trust to be developed with the client businesses, which is important for advice or professional services that can be generally hard to evaluate prior to purchase or experience (Ardley et al., 2016; Beckinsale and Ram, 2006). Building trust in a brand takes time, with Bennett

and colleagues (2000) finding the longer-established Business Link franchises being more trusted than newer franchises.

Brokerage

Based on being a trusted source of information, in 1999 the role of Business Link advisers emphasised brokerage and referral, rather than provision of direct support. A trusted brokerage function can help address the persistent difficulties in navigating the support landscape reported by small business owners. Mole and colleagues (2006) report that different forms of brokerage are associated with different outcomes. Some problems might be resolved quickly through 'light touch' brokerage, while others might benefit from closer 'managed' brokerage relationships, with both being associated with employment growth. Limiting the businesses accessing brokerage, through 'pipeline forcing' did not seem to deliver benefits in isolation, but in combination with 'managed' brokerage was associated with sales growth.

The business support journey

There is value in thinking about support for small businesses in terms of their business support journey, the ways that entrepreneurs and owner-managers access a range of advice and support resources over time (Wapshott and Mallett, 2024). Owner-managers encounter multiple challenges and engage with different sources of support. Support-seeking is not isolated from what has come before or from a sense of future challenges. Mole and colleagues (2006) found that repeated contacts through mailshots, website engagement and direct contacts all led to significant increases in the probability of receiving both intensive and other forms of support. A hub-type service facilitating engagement with business support can engage with such *touch points* (regular contacts within the support ecosystem), which provide an opportunity to signpost wider support availability. This can be extended by utilising *access points*, where users are actively seeking support, offering a diagnostic opportunity to identify wider needs and ascertain growth potential. Finally, such an approach can build on these opportunities to identify and respond to *trigger points*, that is to intervene at a critical moment in a firm's business support journey.

The balance between centralised control and local experimentation

A degree of centralised control is inevitable where there is a need to create and maintain a recognised, trusted national brand that requires particular levels of service to support a high profile. It can be challenging to balance this with a need for local responsiveness and innovation. Franchise management can support localisation and experimentation, but Business Link had low tolerance for the risks of variability in provision. Central government gave Personal Business Advisors targets, including a push towards commercialisation of the service to help reduce the need for government support. This target-driven approach risked damaging the selectivity and focus of the support provision amidst an emphasis on 'selling' Business Link products and services (Lean et al., 1999; Bennett, 2012).

Policy and practice recommendations

This analysis of the historical case study of England's Business Link offers several recommendations for policymakers and business support practitioners. We can think about these recommendations by starting with the dynamic needs of a small business over time, conceived of in relation to their business support journey.

Firstly, a brokerage model can represent a valuable mechanism to maximise the effectiveness of busy markets for business support services over time. This helps facilitate engagement with relevant offers from a market that firms can find difficult to navigate. Matching entrepreneurs and small businesses with high quality services targeted at their specific needs improves efficiency and effectiveness and benefits from this happening at the right time.

To get the right services at the right time, business interactions with support services may differ throughout the business support journey. This is where it is helpful for a brokerage service to make productive use of touch points (regular contacts, signposting support availability), access points (actively seeking support, a diagnostic stage) and trigger points (intervention at a critical juncture) to target support effectively and build trust and sustained, impactful engagement.

Finally, this type of brokerage model can benefit from the trust derived from a national business support brand. The franchise model developed by Business Link offered this while retaining the scope for meeting local needs and to innovate and experiment. However, to work effectively, appropriate targets are required to focus on core objectives and spur innovation, together with effective monitoring and evaluation and channels for sharing best practice.

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